

Employability Skills in the Bangladeshi Readymade Garments Sector

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Abstract

Being the largest industrial sector in Bangladesh, the readymade garments sector has been contributing to the national economy through the wide employment scopes. Despite of that a huge employment opportunity is getting out of our hands due to the deficiencies in required skills in the key positions in this sector. This opportunity is grabbed by our neighbouring countries.

The relevant literature is very poor and weak in describing the required skills for the crucial positions in the RMG sector. However, based on a recent study, a list of 5 key positions in the RMG sector has been used here for identifying the skills requirements.

Through qualitative research, adapting focus group discussion, this paper revealed a skills matrix for the critical positions in the Bangladeshi readymade garments. the paper identified both the soft skills and hard skills required for the best performance.

Key Words: Readymade garments, Employability Skills, Key Positions, Soft Skills, Hard Skills, Employment, Economic Growth

DISCLAIMER:

1. The research methodology section is partially similar with the doctoral dissertation of the first author, available at <https://nova.newcastle.edu.au/vital/access/manager/Repository/uon:39013>
2. The same author group conducted very wide research on Employability Skills in the Bangladeshi RMG sector, and published an article, titled "The Key Positions in the Bangladeshi Readymade Garments Sector", in "Management Development", vol 34, no. 1&2. The published paper and this paper contain few similarities as both are originated from the same research.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The readymade garments, textiles and apparels sectors of Bangladesh have been playing a very vital and precious role in the economic development (Mia and Akter, 2019a). Readymade garments (RMG), in particular, with a very glorious history, has triggered the country's export volume at almost 80% of the total export ([Farhana et al., 2022](#)), ([Islam, 2021](#)). However, it is not reason for contributing to the national economy, the main reason for the contribution is arranging employment opportunity for more than four million people ([Islam, 2021](#)), ([Islam et al., 2016](#)). Therefore, the impact of the RMG sector on the gross domestic product (GDP) through huge employment is undeniable ([Uddin, 2014](#)).

Even though the COVID-19 pandemic could not stop the contribution. A study of the Bangladesh Bank, discloses that the RMG sector has contributed 9.25% to national GDP in the financial year 2021-22 ([Research, 2022](#)); and astonishingly, which was 35.47% higher than the fiscal year 2020-2021 ([Research, 2022](#)).

This vital sector, unfortunately dominated by the foreign nationals ([Tuhin, 2022](#)), ([Noor, 2018](#)). The vital positions are held by them in mid-levels and frequently at the top levels also ([TextileToday, 2017](#)). Not only that the foreigners are getting at least 20% extra salary ([Noor, 2018](#)). Such foreign employment results in \$2 billion yearly remittance to our neighbouring countries ([Fazal and Ahmed, 2020](#)).

Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB) found that the amount of remittance was up to \$3.15 billion ([Manzoor-E-Khoda, 2020](#)). The research also revealed the money was remitted illegally, as the foreign nationals worked on tourist visa.

It has been argued so many occasions that the necessity of maximum involvement of Bangladeshi in the each level of the RMG sector with proper expertise ([Hossian et al., 2019](#)), ([Zaman et al., 2018](#)) in the key positions. Due to our own lacking in skills, the foreign nationals are leading our largest industry. Moreover, the RMG sector is unsuccessful in approaching the graduating students from the Bangladesh universities. Studies revealed that 68% graduates were unwilling to pursue their career in RMG sector ([Fazal and Ahmed, 2020](#)). Altogether, it is critically essential to figure out the skills required for the key positions in the RMG sector.

Though the research is worried with huge foreign employment in the RMG sector of Bangladesh, but it deals with only identifying the required skills for the key positions in the RMG sector.

1.1 Research Gap

The relevant literature of key positions and key skills is very limited and narrow. There is no scholarly paper, based on readymade garments, apparel and textile sectors of

Bangladesh, that describes the explanations of lacking of Bangladeshi nationals' skills. Moreover, few research resulted that the lack of job readiness of Bangladeshi reluctant graduating students twisted the emptiness and which occupied by the foreigners.

1.2 Research Question

This research attempted to explore the required skills for working in the key positions in Bangladeshi RMG sector, so, dealt with a single research question (RQ), as

RQ: What are the employability Skills in the Bangladeshi RMG Sector?

1.2 Objective of the Study

Considering the context and research question, the study dealt with also a single objective linked to the employability skills required for the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

- To explore the skills required to successfully perform the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

1.3 Scope of the Study

The study was limited within the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors of Bangladesh. Furthermore, it focuses on the required skills for the key positions in the RMG sectors, in particular.

1.4 Study Limitations

Though the research was very significant about the skills issues, where the researchers were being inertly stressed for dropping the high unemployment rate in Bangladesh. Time and cost stood as the key blockades.

1.5 Report Structure

The entire report is divided into 5 major chapters; e.g., introduction, literature review, research methodology, findings and discussions, and conclusion. A brief of each chapter provided bellow:

1.5.1 Introduction

The background and rational of the study well explained. After spotting the research gap, particular research objective was developed. The research scope and limitations were described in this chapter.

1.5.2 Literature Review

The literature review chapter included relevant literature. Focusing the skills deficiencies, the literature review advanced with previously identified key positions in the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

1.5.3 Research Methodology

Qualitative research approach was adapted in the research work based on the previous research on key positions of the Bangladeshi RMG sector. For data collection purposes, focus group discussion was expansively deployed as data collection method.

1.5.4 Findings and Discussions

Findings from the focus group discussion with the human resource managers or head of human resource departments of participating readymade garments and textiles were presented. The findings were discussed in the light and in relation to the existing literature.

1.5.5 Conclusions

The final chapter, conclusion, mainly included the concluding remarks. It explored the contribution of the research and prescribed the path for further research.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

With a huge population, Bangladesh is advancing as fast-developing country ([Farid and Mostari, 2022](#)), ([Karim et al., 2022](#)), the total population is around 16.50 crore (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics). Employment and creating employment opportunities are the biggest challenges for this huge population ([Mamun et al., 2020](#)), ([Siddiqui, 2019](#)). The university graduates' negative perception towards social entrepreneurship, as made the employment status very narrow ([Tu et al., 2021](#)), so, it could be a good solution for unemployment, if they occupy themselves in the RMG sector. Currently, foreign nationals are taking such opportunities and exploring the gap in the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

The huge number of foreign nationals employed in the RMG sector in Bangladesh ([Tuhin, 2022](#)) has triggered the study. Therefore, study aims to figure out the skills required to perform the key positions in the RMG sector in Bangladesh, because if the Bangladeshi nationals would apprehend these skills, the foreign employment would be reduced.

2.1 SKILLS DEFICIENCIES

Skills deficiencies in RMG sector are a very common problem in Bangladesh ([Sarker et al., 2019](#)). Particularly, lack in managerial skills and communications skills found as a barrier of employment of the native people ([Wali, 2021](#)).

Researchers find that executives and managers in Bangladeshi RMG sector have been suffering from different skills deficiencies, especially in soft skills ([Sarker et al., 2019](#)), ranging from communication, team work and leadership styles to critical thinking. For better performance of the domestic (Bangladeshi) managers, effective training programs are mandatory in overcoming skills deficiencies ([Islam et al., 2018b](#)). To face the future challenges and ensure more contribution, towards economic growth, such skills deficiencies must be turned into skills sufficiency for improved and productive performance of the managers (Mia and Akter, 2019b).

Different studies reveal various reasons for the skills deficiencies. In some cases, it has been found that job insecurity and, working conditions and stress frequently demotivate employees which results in deficiencies in skills required ([Islam et al., 2018a](#)), ([Akter et al., 2017](#)). Sometimes, lack of opportunities in participation reduces employees' potentials and causes lower performance ([Islam et al., 2017](#)). Furthermore, quality of work life and work-life balance are extremely boiling issues which trigger dissatisfaction among the employees in Bangladeshi RMG sector and decrease working skills ([Islam et al., 2017](#)) and reduce productivity.

Simultaneously, breaching social compliances ([Alam et al., 2018](#)) and improper risk management and prevention issues ([Hasan and Mahmud, 2017](#)) often destroy the employees' attitudes towards their jobs. Poor research and development in product design and development, also stand as obstacles in solving skills deficiencies ([Natasha and Jeny, 2018](#)).

2.2 KEY POSITIONS IN BANGLADESHI RMG SECTOR

Before, focussing the skills required, it was crucial to identify the key positions in the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors. The literature on key positions in the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors proven as very wide and the rate of irrelevancy is too high. On the other hand, different websites, e-magazines etc. revealed that the key or crucial positions in those sectors are line supervisor, sales associate, merchandiser, stylist, public relation specialist, inventory planner, retail buyer, accounts manager, cutting manager, fashion designer, graphics designer, textile designer, stock manager, packing manager, creative director, product developer, technical designer, quality assurance manager, production manager etc. ([Sarkar, 2013](#)), ([Birt, 2023](#)). The list of the positions seems to be irrelevant as all the positions are not directly connected with

the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors. Hence, it became a tough job to identify the true key positions.

Therefore, at this point, the researchers found a previous scholarly paper, that explored the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. A list of 15 key positions were identified (Newaz et al., 2023) as follows:

- 1.** Managing Director or Chief Executive Officer (CEO) or Executive Director (ED)
- 2.** Chief Operating Officer (COO)
- 3.** General Manager or Plan Manager
- 4.** Merchandiser
- 5.** Operations Managers
- 6.** Production Manager
- 7.** Human Resource (HR) Manager
- 8.** Research and Development and/or Product Development
- 9.** Compliance Manager
- 10.** Supply Chain Manager
- 11.** Sustainability Manager
- 12.** Marketing Manager
- 13.** Quality Assurance Manager
- 14.** Store Manager
- 15.** Maintenance Manager

2.3 SKILLS REQUIRED FOR IDENTIFIED POSITIONS

Based on the previous research (Newaz et al., 2023), 15 positions were identified. Through further research, these 15 positions were analysed in terms of importance. For satisfying the research objective, it was necessary to point out the required skills for the identified positions.

Due to difficulties in literature searching for each position to find required skills and time limitations, the researchers accumulated available skills for each position from different web sources. The list of skills and related positions are presented below in table - 1.

SL	POSITION	REQUIRED SKILLS
01.	Managing Director or CEO or ED	Strategic Leadership Creativity Motivation Communication Team Management Interpersonal Collaborative Problem-solving Critical Thinking Decision-making Presentation
02.	Chief Operating Officer (COO)	Strategic Leadership Creativity Motivation Communication Team Management Interpersonal Collaborative Problem-solving Critical Thinking Decision-making Presentation
03.	General Manager or Plant Manger	Strategic Leadership Motivation Communication Team Management Interpersonal Organizing Collaborative Problem-solving Decision-making Presentation Technical

Table - 01 : List of Skills for Different Positions

SL	POSITION	REQUIRED SKILLS
04.	Merchandiser	Commercial Confidence Cope with pressure Teamworking Communication Interpersonal Leadership Numerical Analytical
05.	Operations Managers	Strategic Leadership Motivation Communication Team Management Risk Analysis Time Management Interpersonal Organizing Collaborative Adaptability Problem-solving Decision-making Technical
06.	Production Manager	Creativity Analytical Numeracy Coordination Cost Analytics Scheduling Leadership Communication Interpersonal Team Player Time Management Attention to Details
07.	HR Manager	Analytical Problem-solving Leadership Motivation Team Management Communication Interpersonal Negotiation Technical
08.	R & D or Product Development	Analytical Diagnostic Communication Team Player Numeracy ICT Research

Table – 01 : List of Skills for Different Positions (cont.)

SL	POSITION	REQUIRED SKILLS
09.	Compliance Manager	Analytical Attention to Details Interpersonal People Management Leadership Team Player Legal Documentation
10.	Supply Chain Manager	Communication Creativity Attention to Details e-Business Interpersonal Team Management Logistic Time Management Adaptability Inventory Sourcing
11.	Sustainability Manager	Analysing Impacts Sustainability Planning Environment Protection Attention to Details Interpersonal Team Player Corporate Ethics Documentation
12.	Marketing Manager	Analytical Creativity Ability to Prioritise Product Promoting Advertising Team Management Communication Research Presentation Numeracy ICT People Management
13.	Quality Assurance Manager	Analytical Designing Implementing Negotiating Customer Handling Communication Interpersonal Team Player Conflict Management Time Management Attention to Details

Table – 01 : List of Skills for Different Positions (cont.)

SL	POSITION	REQUIRED SKILLS
14.	Store Manager	Inventory Management Numeracy ICT Communication Interpersonal Team Player Attention to Details
15.	Maintenance Manager	Interpersonal Time Management Know How to Groom Individuals Problem Solving Skills. ... Flexibility Team Work Technical Expertise

Table – 1 illustrated the possible employability skills required for identified 15 positions (Newaz et al., 2023) in the ready-made garments, apparels and textile sectors. The list of employability skills was examined and processed through further research. The finally selected skills for different positions were described in the light of relevant literature.

3.0 METHODOOOGY

Research methods, research design and research approach are the integral parts of a good and sound research methodology that are used for collecting, analysing and interpreting data with specific plans; addressing the research problems and for satisfying the research question and objectives ([Creswell, 2014](#)).

Therefore, the research approaches and the research design with the appropriate research method are specified in this section.

3.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

To begin with, philosophical considerations directly influence the research practice though these remains hidden in the research ([Slife et al., 1995](#)) and scholars have suggested to prepare explicit research plans with philosophical exposure ([Creswell, 2014](#)).

In his book, John W. Creswell, has termed philosophical considerations as philosophical worldviews which was an orientation towards general philosophy considering the nature of research that researchers convey to studies ([Creswell, 2014](#)).

The postpositivist worldview considers traditional research arrangement holding more justification for quantitative research than qualitative research, while the constructivist view, often termed as social constructivism, refers to usual qualitative research approach ([Creswell, 2014](#)). On the other hand, transformative worldview is engaged in confronting societal coercion through embracing research investigation required for entwined politics and political revolution schemas, while the pragmatic worldview rises out of activities, circumstances and concerns rather than predecessor situations and is worried for applications that work towards problem-solving adopting both quantitative and qualitative research methods ([Creswell, 2014](#)).

3.2 REARCH METHOD

Considering the philosophical views, this research matched with the constructivism, e.g., qualitative research; because, it was categorized as an inclusivity research ([Abbasi et al., 2016](#)). As the research focussed on identifying the crucial positions and required skills for the position identified, inclusiveness ([Nilholm and Göransson, 2017](#)) and explorative ([Dana and Dumez, 2015](#)) were the features of this qualitative research.

The skills required in the key positions in RMG sector in Bangladesh are identifiable through qualitative research, because the study belongs to social constructivism philosophy which refers to traditional qualitative research ([Creswell, 2014](#)).

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design refers to the entire design of the research based on the research method ([Dannels, 2018](#)). Research approach, data collection method, research framework ([Tobi and Kampen, 2018](#)) and sampling all are encompassed within research design ([Abutabenjeh and Jaradat, 2018](#)), ([Rahi, 2017](#)).

Altogether, research design is the core of every research. In this research, the research designed as qualitative research with following research approach, data collection method, research framework and sampling.

3.3.1 Research Approach

Plans and processes are included in the research approach that narrow-down extensive assumptions into a precise way for collecting, analysing and interpreting data ([Creswell, 2014](#)) and selection of research approaches totally related and dependent on the nature of research problems.

The current research, aimed to identify the skills required for the key positions in the RMG, apparels, textile sectors, it proposed as qualitative research. Accordingly, data collection method, sampling and data analysis plans were developed.

3.3.2 Data Collection Method

Considering different qualitative data collection methods; e.g. in-depth interviews, convergent interviews, case study, focus group discussions ([McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015](#)), ([Wolgemuth et al., 2015](#)), ([Bhattacharjee, 2012](#)), ([Rao and Perry, 2003](#)); this research adopts the suitable one.

The synergetic effects as well as ensuring the outcomes ([Rao and Perry, 2003](#)) were regarded as the fundamental reasons for choosing focus group discussions. Comparing the benefits and weaknesses of different qualitative methods of data collection, the research deployed *online focus group discussions* for collecting data. The circumstances of the current research sufficiently described, and in such situation, focus group discussions was the best to deploy ([Hennink, 2013](#)), ([Moretti et al., 2011](#)), ([Bertrand et al., 1992](#)), and it would be an enjoyable experience for the group members sharing their thoughts and insights, and as well as for the researchers ([Colucci, 2007](#)).

3.4.3 Research Framework

Research framework is a reflection of the research approach ([Tobi and Kampen, 2018](#)) that indicates the goal of the research. The entire flows of research activities are usually expressed through a diagram in such framework ([Biermann and Kalfagianni, 2020](#)).

The following diagram depicts the framework of this research.

Figure – 1 : Research Framework

3.4.4 Sampling

The study conducted qualitative research where focus group discussion was the data collection method. There are around 4,000 readymade garments in Bangladesh ([BIDA, 2022](#)). Participants for focus group discussions were randomly selected as referred to the simple sampling technique (Cochran, 2007). Apart from this it ensured that participation of at least couple of giant RMG factories support the sampling effectively (Sharma, 2017).

The ideal number of a focus group ranges from 6 to 8 ([Robinson, 2020](#)), ([Krueger et al., 2000](#)) which can be extended up to 12 ([Khan et al., 1991](#)). This research engaged 12 participants in the focus group discussion.

3.4.5 Sampling Frame

All the ready-made garments factories, apparels and textile mills registered with either Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) or Bangladesh Knitwear Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BKMEA) or Bangladesh Textile Mills Association (BTMA) considered as the sampling frame in this study.

Currently, over 4,000 ready-made garments and apparels factories are running in Bangladesh (source: BGMEA and BIDA) along with 1,780 textile mills (source: BTMA).

3.4.6 Study Location

The study covers all the readymade garments, apparels and textiles registered with BGMEA, BKMEA and BMTA in Bangladesh.

3.4.7 Respondent Groups

The divisional heads, or at least the assistant managers of the human resource department were the respondents for this research. They actively participated in the focus group discussion.

3.4.8 Data Analysis Plan

The research collected information through focus group discussions. The qualitative data, derived from the FGD, analysed qualitatively and manually.

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Triggered by a well-composed research methodology, the researchers conducted a focus group discussion (FDG) with the head or manager or assistant managers of different ready-made garments.

In the FGD, a list of skills for all possible skills (accordingly table-1) for the identified and confirmed key positions (Newaz et al., 2023) from first FGD. The participants were requested to work on the common skills and particular position-oriented skills; and exercised for ranging from the most crucial skills to the least.

The findings and discussions were presented in separately in this, while the findings were bit elaborated with little analysis.

4.1 FINDINGS

There were very successful and enthusiastic focus group discussions regarding the required skills for the key positions in the ready-made garments (RMG) sector of Bangladesh. The findings of focus group discussion described in following sub-section.

4.1.1 Different Skills in the Key Positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector

A list of skills for the 15 key positions identified, was provided to the participants of the second focus group discussions. They were allowed to include, as well as exclude, any skill, if they experienced or identified necessary (or unnecessary). A very interactive discussion was made on required skills for the 15 key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

The participants were very enthusiastic and active in discussing and cross checking with each other. After a long debate, the participants divided the required skills into 2 groups; common skills (soft skills) and position-oriented skills (hard skills).

As the common skills or soft skills, the participants summarized and agreed on the following skills:

Positions : ALL KEY POSITIONS

Soft Skills : Communication, ICT or Tech Savvy, Interpersonal, Leading, Motivation, Presentation and Team Leader/Member.

After finalizing the common or soft skills for all the key positions, the participants in the focus group discussions, finalized skills for every key position. These skills were completely position-oriented, and therefore, they termed these skills as hard skills.

Position : Managing Director or CEO or ED

Hard Skills : Collaborative, Creative Thinking, Creativity, Decision-making, Far-sighted, Financing, Networking, Problem-solving, Strategic.

Position : Chief Operating Officer (COO)

Hard Skills : Analyzing Situation, Change Management, Collaborative, Creative Thinking, Creativity, Decision-making, Planning, Problem-solving, Risk Management, Strategic.

Position : General Manager or Plant Manager

Hard Skills : Collaborative, Decision-making, Organizing, Problem-solving, Strategic, Technical - Operations and Production.

Position : Merchandiser

Hard Skills : Attention to Details, Convincing, Decision-making, Negotiating, Numeracy, Product Analyst, Sourcing.

Position : Operations Manager

Hard Skills : Adaptability, Collaborative, Data Management, Decision-making, Lean Management, Organizing, Problem-solving, Product Development, Risk Analysis, Talent Nourishing, Technical - Factory Operations.

Position : Production Manager

Hard Skills : Analytical, Attention to Details, Coordination, Cost Analyst, Creativity, Decision-making, Lean Management, Numeracy, People Management, Scheduling, Technical - machine, layout etc., Troubleshooting.

Position : Human Resource Manager

Hard Skills : Active Listener, Advocacy, Analytical, Attention to Details, Collaborative, Conflict Handling, Counselling, HR Planning, Negotiation, Problem-solving, Technical - laws, legislation, documentation etc., Trainer.

Position : Research and Development or Product Development

Hard Skills : Analytical, Creativity, Diagnostic, Numeracy, Product Knowledge, Product Risk Analysis, Research, Sustainability, Technical - research methods and techniques etc.

Position : Compliance Manager

Hard Skills : Analytical, Assessor, Attention to Details, Audit, Critical Thinking, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Ethical Sourcing, People Management, Technical - legal, buyers' code of conduct (BCOC), documentation etc.

Position : Supply Chain Manager

Hard Skills : Attention to Details, Budgeting, Creativity, Data Analysis, Decision-making, e-Business, Forecasting, Logistic, Negotiating, Sourcing, Supplier Evaluation.

Position : Sustainability Manager

Hard Skills : Analyzing Impacts, Attention to Details, Compliance, Corporate Ethics, Documentation, Environment Protection, Financing, HR Issues, Resource Efficiency, Strong Communication with Top management, Sustainability Planning, Waste Management.

Position : Marketing Manager

Hard Skills : Ability to Prioritize, Advertising, Analytical, Attention to Details, Competitor Analysis, Creativity, Customer Orientation, Forecasting, Research, Numeracy, People Management, Product Promoting.

Position : Quality Assurance Manager

Hard Skills : Analytical, Assuring Zero-Defect, Attention to Details, Buyers Handling, Conflict Handling, Designing, Implementing, Inspecting, Negotiating, Problem-solving, Quality Managing, Strategic.

Position : Store Manager

Hard Skills : Attention to Details, Compliance, Decision-making, Documentation, Inventory Management, Logistic Authority, Numeracy, Work under Pressure.

Position : Maintenance Manager

Hard Skills : Analytical, Attention to Details, Compliance, Coordination, Cost Analyst, Creativity, Numeracy, Scheduling, Sourcing, Sustainability, Technical - production arrangement with machinery etc., Training.

The exercise and discussion in the second focus group were very rigorous and fruitful. All the possible employability skills for the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector were very carefully identified and finalized. The following section illustrated an at a glance presentation of all the required skills by the selected 15 key positions.

4.2 EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS IN THE KEY POSITIONS IN BANGLADESHI RMG SECTOR

Firstly, as identified in the focus group discussion, the list of common skills, termed as soft skills, for all the 15 key positions are listed below:

- ✓ Communication
- ✓ ICT or Tech Savvy
- ✓ Interpersonal
- ✓ Leading
- ✓ Motivation
- ✓ Presentation
- ✓ Team Leader/Member

The position-oriented skills, termed as hard skills, are listed through a matrix table (skill matrix) below:

Serial Number	List of Skills	KEY POSITIONS														
		MD/CEO/ED	COO	GM/Plant Manager	Merchandiser	Operations	Production	Human Resource	R & D	Compliance	Supply Chain	Sustainability	Marketing	Quality Assurance	Store	Maintenance
1	Ability to Prioritize											√				
2	Active Listener							√								
3	Adaptability					√										
4	Advertising											√				
5	Advocacy						√									
6	Analysing Impacts											√				
7	Analytical					√	√	√	√			√	√			√
8	Analyzing Situation		√													
9	Assessor									√						
10	Assuring Zero-Defect													√		
11	Attention to Details				√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
12	Audit									√						
13	Budgeting										√					
14	Buyers Handling													√		
15	Change Management		√													
16	Collaborative	√	√	√		√	√									
17	Competitor Analysis											√				
18	Compliance										√				√	√
19	Conflict Handling						√						√			
20	Convincing				√											

Table - 2 : List of Position-oriented Skills for the Key Positions

Serial Number	List of Skills	KEY POSITIONS														
		MD/CEO/ED	COO	GM/Plant Manager	Merchandiser	Operations	Production	Human Resource	R & D	Compliance	Supply Chain	Sustainability	Marketing	Quality Assurance	Store	Maintenance
21	Coordination						√									√
22	Corporate Ethics											√				
23	Cost Analyst						√									√
24	Counselling							√								
25	Creative Thinking	√	√							√						
26	Creativity	√	√				√		√		√		√			√
27	CSR									√						
28	Customer Orientation												√			
29	Data Analysis										√					
30	Data Management					√										
31	Decision-making	√	√	√	√	√	√				√				√	
32	Designing														√	
33	Diagnostic								√							
34	Documentation											√			√	
35	e-Business										√					
36	Environment Protection											√				
37	Ethical Sourcing									√						
38	Far-sighted	√														
39	Financing	√										√				
40	Forecasting										√		√			
41	HR Issues											√				
42	HR Planning							√								
43	Implementing														√	
44	Inspecting														√	
45	Inventory Management														√	
46	Lean Management					√	√									
47	Logistics										√					
48	Logistic Authority														√	
49	Negotiating				√			√			√			√		
50	Networking	√														
51	Numeracy				√		√		√				√		√	√
52	Organizing			√		√										
53	People Management						√			√			√			
54	Planning		√													
55	Problem-solving	√	√	√		√		√						√		
56	Product Analyst				√											
57	Product Development					√										

Table – 2 : List of Position-oriented Skills for the Key Positions (*cont.*)

Serial Number	List of Skills	KEY POSITIONS														
		MD/CEO/ED	COO	GM/Plant Manager	Merchandiser	Operations	Production	Human Resource	R & D	Compliance	Supply Chain	Sustainability	Marketing	Quality Assurance	Store	Maintenance
58	Product Knowledge								0				□			
59	Product Promoting												√			
60	Product Risk Analysis								√							
61	Quality Managing													√		
62	Research								√				√			
63	Resource Efficiency											√				
64	Risk Analysis					√										
65	Risk Management		√													
66	Scheduling						√									√
67	Sourcing				√						√					√
68	Strategic	√	√	√										√		
69	Strong Communication with Top management											√				
70	Supplier Evaluation										√					
71	Sustainability								√							√
72	Sustainability Planning										√					
73	Talent Nourishing					√										
74	Technical - Factory Operations					√										
75	Technical - Laws, Legislation, Documentation							√								
76	Technical - Legal, Buyers' Code of Conduct, Documentation								√							
77	Technical - Operations and Production			√												
77	Technical - Operations and Production			√												
78	Technical - Production Arrangements with Machinery															√
79	Technical - Research Methods & Techniques								√							
80	Technical (machine, layout etc.)						√									
81	Trainer							√								√
82	Troubleshooting						√									
83	Waste Management										√					
84	Work under Pressure														√	

Table – 2 : List of Position-oriented Skills for the Key Positions (*cont.*)

Total 90 employability skills for 15 key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG were identified through focus group discussions. Out of 90, 6 skills are common for all positions, calling

as soft skills whereas rest 84 are position-oriented, termed as hard skills. Further discussions made available in the following section.

The participants of the both focus group discussion were human resource professionals, working in the RMG and textile sectors of Bangladesh. Their opinions, thoughts, insights and experience are the foundation of identifying the employability skills in the selected 15 key positions.

The participants also added that the successful performance in the key positions depends on the outstanding execution of the skills, identified for a particular position, considering both the soft skills and hard skills.

IMPORTANT NOTES

- 1) It was revealed from the focus group discussion that any lacking in the soft skills impacts highly on the hard skills in performance and accomplishment.
- 2) The participants of the both focus group discussions enforced on an issue that the skills variety is very wide in the RMG sector in Bangladesh. Naturally, it became tough to employ a person with 10/12 hard skills (position-oriented) along with 6 soft skills. In case of foreign nationals, it found that they furnished themselves with the required skills for the key position in the RMG sector. These reasons kept them ahead from the Bangladeshi people regarding employment in the key positions in the RMG sector.

4.3 DISCUSSIONS

Discussions on the skills requirements for the key positions also driven by the thoughts and insights of the focus group participants. Based on the discussion in focus groups, the researchers divided the skills into 2 categories; common and position-specific. All the thoughts, perceptions, and insights were well acknowledged and supported by the body of knowledge.

4.3.1 Employability Skills in the Key Positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector

The focus group discussions resulted into exploration of variety of skills for the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. Among 90 identified skills, 6 were termed as “soft skills” whereas 84 were termed as “hard skills”.

Soft skills are usually people-oriented, personal – intangible skills ([Matteson et al., 2016](#)). These soft skills are very vibrant for understanding, relating and performing the task-oriented skills ([Jones et al., 2017](#)). Therefore, soft skills require proper attention and concentration, as the skills are though common but difficult to adapt ([Clarke, 2016](#)). Particularly, the graduates should be very aware in attaining and capturing the soft skills for their better employment opportunities ([Succi and Canovi, 2020](#)).

Different researchers have identified and classified multiple soft skills. But the majority have argued that skills in *communication* (Maturro et al., 2019), (Kahlon, 2013), *ICT or Tech Savvy* (Hettiarachchi et al., 2023), (Harrison, 2017), *interpersonal* (Cerezo-Narváez et al., 2018), (Beenen and Pichler, 2016), *leading* (Cichosz et al., 2020), (Bates and Morgan, 2018), *motivation* (Chien et al., 2020), (Bao and Nizam, 2015), *presentation* (Vasanthakumari, 2019), (John and Arthi, 2016), and *team leader/member* (Juárez et al., 2021), (Cizmaş et al., 2020), the most common (Groeneveld et al., 2020), (Maturro et al., 2019), (Gibert et al., 2017).

On the other hand, hard skills are referred to those techniques and know-how, required to perform a job successfully (Ezzat, 2017). Hard skills are easily measurable (Starcher and Allen, 2016) and tangible as well (Rosenberg, 2022). Both the hard skills and soft skills are interrelated (Balcar, 2016); to be very specific, in the most cases, hard skills are dependent on the soft skills (Asbari et al., 2020), (Cimatti, 2016).

Through the focus group discussions, the researchers accumulated 84 hard skills for 15 different key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. All the skills were not for all the positions. Different positions required different hard skills from the list of 84.

A **managing director or chief executive officer or executive director** should possess the skills of *collaborative, creative thinking, creativity* (Carmeli and Paulus, 2015), *decision-making, far-sighted* (Piwowar-Sulej, 2021), *financing, networking* (Okello Candiya Bongomin et al., 2018), *problem-solving and strategic* (Rahman, 2019). The **chief operating officer** needs to be proficient in analyzing situation, change management, collaborative (He et al., 2017), *creative thinking, creativity* (Wahyudi et al., 2020), *decision-making, planning, problem-solving* (Gippoliti and Battisti, 2017), *risk management and strategic* (Kim et al., 2021). A **general manager, or plant manager**, requires to dominate in *collaborative, decision-making, organizing* (Wong et al., 2015), *problem-solving, strategic* (Megheirkouni, 2017), and *technically sound in operations and production processes* (Villena and Gioia, 2018), (Bartlett and Ghoshal, 2017). These positions usually belong to the top management in the RMG sector.

Other 12 key positions' e.g., merchandiser, operations manager, production manager, human resource manager, research and development, compliance manager, supply chain manager, sustainability manager, marketing manager, quality assurance manager, store manager, maintenance manager; usually remain with the middle level management of the RMG sector in Bangladesh (Islam and Islam, 2020), (Tareque and Islam, 2020).

A **merchandiser** in a ready-made garment should be equipped with the skills of *attention to details, convincing* (Kakde and Kumbhar, 2019), *decision-making, negotiating, numeracy* (Testa and Karpova, 2022), *product analyst and sourcing* (Familmaleki et al., 2015). An **operations manager** must be sound in *adaptability, collaborative* (Berkes, 2017), *data management* (Wright, 2017), *decision-making, lean management* (Bai et al., 2019), *organizing, problem-solving, product development* (Worley and Doolen, 2015), *risk analysis* (Aven, 2016), *talent nourishing* (Kayes et al., 2018), *technically proficient in factory operations* (Trentin et al., 2019). The **production managers** are highly expected to be talented in *analytical, attention to details,*

coordination (Jandaghi et al., 2019), *cost analyst, creativity, decision-making* (Bagshaw, 2019), *numeracy, troubleshooting, people management* (Jandaghi et al., 2019), *lean management, scheduling* (Sahoo, 2020), and *technically dominant in - machinery, equipment, layout etc.* (Rathi et al., 2016).

The managers working in the **human resource** function, have to be extraordinary in *active listening, analytical ability, problem-solving* (Chowdhury and Anon, 2021), *HR planning* (Khan, 2020), attention to details, collaboration, conflict handling (Khan and Roy, 2023), (Khan et al., 2019), *training, counselling* (Haque and Nishat, 2022), *advocacy, negotiation* (Hossain and Ahmad, 2020) and *technical knowledge - laws, legislation, documentation etc.* (Rashid et al., 2019). **Research and Development** (product development) managers should be proficient with *analytical, creativity, diagnostic* (Sinkovics et al., 2018), *numeracy, product knowledge, product risk analysis* (Hasan et al., 2020), *research, sustainability* (Camilleri et al., 2023) and *technical issues, e.g., - research methods and techniques etc.* (Mohibullah et al., 2018). **Compliance managers** in the RMG sector should be able to practice the skills of *analytical, critical thinking* (Saha et al., 2021), attention to details, people management (Alam et al., 2017), *assessor, audit* (Hemphill and White III, 2018), *corporate social responsibility (CSR), ethical sourcing* (Akter, 2015) and *technical knowledge in legal, buyers' code of conduct (BCOC), documentation* etc. (Uddin et al., 2022).

The **supply chain managers** must be well practising in *attention to details, creativity, data analysis* (Habib et al., 2020), *budgeting, decision-making, negotiating* (Handfield et al., 2020), *logistic* (Velikova, 2015), *forecasting, e-business* (Stefanus and Hartono, 2018), *sourcing and supplier evaluation* (Antonini et al., 2020). **Sustainability managers** should be well equipped in *analyzing impacts, attention to details, documentation* (Sarkar et al., 2020a), *environment protection, sustainability planning, resource efficiency, waste management* (Aziz et al., 2020), *compliance, corporate ethics, financing* (Dutta et al., 2019), *HR issues and strong communication with top management* (Islam et al., 2020). All the **marketing managers** in the Bangladeshi RMG sector must possess top skills in *attention to details, analytical, competitor analysis* (Sarkar et al., 2020a), *ability to prioritize, creativity* (Sarker et al., 2019), *advertising, product promoting, customer orientation* (Sarkar et al., 2020b), *forecasting, research, numeracy and people management* (Rahman and Chowdhury, 2022), (Thongrak et al., 2021).

Quality assurance managers are asked to perform well in several skills, such as *attention to details, analytical, strategic* (Talapatra et al., 2019), *assuring zero-defect* (Palgunadi et al., 2022), *conflict handling, negotiating, problem-solving* (Sarker et al., 2019), *designing, implementing, inspecting* (Bheda, 2021), *buyers handling, quality managing* (Hoque et al., 2020). A **store manager** is supposed to be a well performer in *attention to details, decision-making* (Ahad et al., 2021a), *documentation, compliance* (Khan et al., 2017), *inventory management, logistic authority* (Paul et al., 2022), *numeracy and work under pressure* (Ahad et al., 2021b). All the **maintenance managers** in the RMG sector must have good skills in *analytical, attention to details, creativity* (Rashid et al., 2016), *coordination* (Mishra and Mishra, 2018), *training* (Akter and Alam, 2016), *cost analyst, numeracy* (Gul et al., 2022), *scheduling, sourcing* (Hossain and

Roy, 2016), *compliance, sustainability* (Alam et al., 2018) and sufficient *technical knowledge in production arrangement with machinery etc.* (Islam et al., 2018b).

All the hard skills for the key positions described with the support from the body of knowledge. Across the globe, all the skills for the identified key positions are well emphasized.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Being the most vital industrial sector for Bangladeshi economy, the ready-made garments (RMG) is crucial for the employment opportunities rather than export orientation. The RMG sector plays a vibrant role in the economy by accommodating and creating the largest employment.

To reduce the unemployment rate in Bangladesh through maximizing the employment in this sector is only possible with skilled and trained people. So, it is not impossible to train and skilled-up the large population without a skills matrix in the key positions to participate in the RMG sector.

If the skills requirements for the key positions are not clear and open, it is not possible to employ the people to foster the economy and to reduce the unemployment rate.

5.1 RESEARCH WORK AND OUTCOMES

The research was inspired and attempted to identify the employability skills in the key positions of ready-made garments sector.

Starting with a list of key positions in the RMG sector, the researchers decided to deploy focus group discussion for identification of the skills requirements.

A focus group discussion was arranged through zoom platform. 12 garments and textiles participated in the focus group discussion. Managers and executives of different levels of human resource department in those organizations actively and enthusiastically participated, and mentionable is that voluntarily.

The focus group discussions resulted in identification of 90 required skills for those positions. Among them 6 were termed as “soft skills” and 84 as hard skills. It was significantly added that all the hard skills become valueless if the soft skills are not properly exercised.

5.2 CONCLUSION ABOUT THE RESEARCH TOPIC

“Employability Skills for the Key Positions: Bangladeshi RMG Sector Context”

The selected topic for the research was very clear. It dealt with the identification of required skills for employability in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

To get the skills, the researchers arranged a focus group discussion and verified the identified skills with the literature support.

Identification of these skills could assist the policy makers in empowering Bangladeshi people to be engaged more for reducing unemployment rate as well as boosting up the economic growth of the country.

A thoughtful deployment of this topic was to find out the employability skills in the key positions across the Bangladeshi RMG sector through an investigating research methodology resulted in figuring out the required skills and that may allow an opportunity to train Bangladeshi people and make them capable for the significant positions in the sector.

5.3 CONCLUSION ABOUT THE RESEARCH QUESTION

The research was concern about identifying the skills essential for the Bangladeshi RMG sector, particularly in the key positions. Hence, the research question was presented as

What are the employability Skills in the Bangladesh RMG Sector?

The research question was successfully and completely answered through identification of the required employable skills in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

5.4 CONCLUSION ABOUT THE RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

To answer the research question, it was required to explore and find the employable skills in the key positions. Therefore, the research objective was written as follow:

- To explore the skills required for successfully perform the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

The objective was satisfactorily fulfilled through exploring and identifying of the the required skills for performing the best on the key positions.

5.5 RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The research brought out the employable skills in the most significant positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. This list of skills has a very wide application. The government,

the graduates, the recruiters and the skills developing institutions can use for their own policies, guidelines and development issues.

5.5.1 Contribution to the Body of Knowledge

The literature of the ready-made garments, particularly, in Bangladesh issue, has received a very rich and in-depth research on the employable skills in the key positions. Hence, it can be confidently claim that the researchers have enriched the literature.

5.5.2 Contribution to Practices

Practitioners of different categories shall be benefited from this research. The government can develop a skills development policy for the RMG sector so that Bangladeshi people can easily capture those skills for employment. Simultaneously, the fresh graduates can design their own with these skills so that they appear as the most suitable candidates for the key positions in the RMG sector.

The recruiting agencies can use the skills list for redesigning their job specification with more clarifications. Different training institutions can use this list to design their training program so that the programs will be completely position specific.

5.6 SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This research has opened several significant scopes for the further research and applications.

Firstly, the skills list can be analyzed and measured in terms of existence among Bangladeshi people. It will help in understanding the level of skills gap in the RMG sector.

Secondly, the list can serve a tool for developing job specifications for the key positions and the graduates will be able to concentrate on the required skills.

Thirdly, initiatives for making the skills available among Bangladeshi people so that they become empowered in working the RMG sector and in higher number.

5.7 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The research successfully identified the employability skills in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. It detailed out that if the skills are made available among Bangladeshi, they can lead the RMG sector with firm confidence and solidity.

The research question was reasonably and adequately answered. The research objective was satisfied completely and backed the nation toward possible prosperity.

In the concluding remark, it can be confidently stated that this research has substantially verified very precious for the Bangladeshi RMG sector in developing own capabilities for

serving at the leading positions. Importantly, the attitude of the graduates towards the RMG jobs must be changed for meeting the challenges in the coming days.

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